

100 Households, 100 Circular Stories: Inspiring Sustainable Living in Europe

Deliverable 2.2: Methodology development for assessing the psychological and behavioural effects of the intervention

Delivery year: 2025

Project number	101135495		Project acronym	CircleUp
Full project title	100 Households, 100 Circular Stories: Inspiring Sustainable Living in Europe			
Project URL	circle-up.eu			
EU project adviser	Erik Pentimalli			
Deliverable number	D2.2	Title	Methodology development for assessing the psychological and behavioural effects of the intervention	
Work package number	WP2	Title	Development of conceptual framework and methodology	
Dissemination level	PU – Public			

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101135495.

UK participants in Horizon Europe Project CircleUp are supported by UKRI grant numbers: 10115495 Oxfordshire County Council and 10110987 Earthwatch Europe.

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Revision History

Version #	Implemented by	Revision Date	Description of changes
V0.1	Stephen Parkinson	15.08.25	Minor changes

Approval Procedure

Version #	Deliverable Name	Approved by	Institution	Approval Date

Table of contents

Abstract	4
1 Introduction	5
1.1 CircleUp	5
1.2 Methodologies used in CircleUp	6
1.2.1 Quantitative methods	6
1.2.2 Qualitative methods	7
2 Recruitment questionnaire	7
2.1 Overall purpose	7
2.2 Stipulated length	8
2.3 Recruitment questions	9
3 Questionnaires	9
3.1 Pre-intervention	10
3.1.1 Overall purpose	10
3.1.2 Stipulated length	10
3.1.3 Implementation	10
3.1.4 Questions	10
3.2 Other interventions	23
4 LCA	24
5 Circular stories evaluation	27
6 Group discussion	28
6.1 Overall purpose	28
6.2 Interview guide and procedures	29
7 Individual interviews	31
7.1 Overall purpose	31
7.2 Interview guide and procedures	31
8 Behaviour observation	34
9 Conclusion	37
10 References	38

List of figures

Figure 1. Timeline figure of the CircleUp activities including the survey measurement points.

List of tables

Table 1. Questions for the recruitment questionnaire

Table 2. Questions for the quantitative surveys

Table 3. Questions for the LCA studies

Table 4. Interview guidelines for the group discussions

Table 5. Interview guidelines for the individual interviews

Table 6. Questions for the behaviour observation

Table 7. Household visit checklist

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full text
CE	Circular Economy
WP	Working Package
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
GHG	Greenhouse Gases

Abstract

This document outlines the different activities that are part of Deliverable 2.2, which falls under Working Package 2 of the CircleUp project. As specified in the CircleUp project proposal, Deliverable 2.2 includes the “Methodology development for assessing the psychological and behavioural effects of the intervention”. First, the overall goal of the CircleUp project is presented. Second, the document provides information on the recruitment strategy, the criteria for household selection and a detailed plan to reach the potential 100 households. Furthermore, this document will elaborate on both the quantitative and the qualitative data collection methods of the project, including LCA studies, circular stories, and the survey and interview questions that will be used during the intervention, scheduled in 2026.

1 Introduction

This document provides an overview of the different methodological approaches that have been developed to assess the psychological and behavioural effects of the tailored circular economy intervention package that will be used in the CircleUp project in at least 100 households. It builds upon the work presented in the first deliverable of the CircleUp project, D2.1. This first deliverable forms the basis for understanding household behavioural changes and attitudes in the transition toward a circular economy at the household level. It introduces the project's conceptual framework based on Bamberg's (2013) Stage Model of Self-Regulated Behavioural Change (SSBC) and is supported by a comprehensive literature review. The first deliverable also summarizes the outcomes of the different workshops that have been conducted throughout the project. It also presents the concept for the CircleUp app concept and outlines its functionalities. Furthermore, it also gives an overview of the identified sixteen behavioural challenges that will be used throughout the project.

The first chapter of this deliverable starts with giving a brief overview of the objectives of the CircleUp project while Chapter 2 describes the recruitment methods for the selection of the participating households. Chapter 3 discusses the quantitative methods. The quantitative methods include four surveys and are designed to measure a wide range of data among all household members aged 14 years and older, including a baseline questionnaire, an in-between questionnaire, a post intervention questionnaire, and a follow-up questionnaire. Chapter 4 focuses on the LCA and aims to determine the potential reduction of environmental impact to households participating in the challenges and thus having savings of food, textile products, packaging and electronics respectively. To assess the reduced environmental impact of each challenge, the households have to track their savings within the CircleUp app. This results in a better understanding of the quantity of savings and its associated change in behaviour of the households, in particular their circular economy practices within the domains of food waste, packaging, electronic devices, and textiles. Chapter 5 describes the circular stories methodology and explains how the stories will be evaluated in the project. Chapter 6 and 7 discusses qualitative methods and describes both the group interviews and the individual interviews. The interviews are important to gain a better understanding of the households' experiences, attitudes, and perspectives on the circular economy practices that are part of the tailored intervention package. In Chapter 8, the reader can find more information about the behaviour observation method and how it will be used in the project. Finally, Chapter 9 gives a brief conclusion of the deliverable.

1.1 CircleUp

CircleUp is a highly innovative endeavour that aims to increase the diffusion rate of circular practices at the micro level, as a vital step towards achieving a circular economy, optimising material streams into and out of households and closing the loops wherever possible. It seeks to achieve this goal by developing, testing, implementing, evaluating, disseminating an innovative behavioural intervention package consisting of consultation and information, gamification, and feedback approaches, supplemented by a technical solution to provide this intervention package. With this innovative behavioural approach, the project will shape social norms by promoting communication and encouraging participants to question the status quo. It will establish and foster the social identification of individuals as circular citizens, inviting them to engage in and organise group activities that reinforce sustainable social norms and discourage unsustainable habits. The project will leverage an innovative technology tool to stimulate and channel interactions, allowing participants to engage with people beyond their direct circle of neighbours or friends. By sharing social circular stories and participating in group activities, participants will not only strengthen social bonds and satisfy the need for social connection and self-esteem. Interactive Learning Environments and simulation tools will support the transfer of insights and develop competencies for integrated analysis and model-based assessments of key sustainable consumption policy and practice topics. System dynamics model-based tools will support scoping

and appraisal of strategies and policies related to sustainable consumption. The success of this intervention package in 100 model households in four structurally and culturally different countries will demonstrate CircleUp's potential to transform the way people consume, how they can benefit from the circular economy, and reduce social disparity, environmental footprints, and GHG emissions.

As outlined above, the CircleUp project aims to develop an innovative behavioural tailored intervention package to promote circular economy practices among households, on both the individual and the collective level. More specifically, we want to foster a circular economy by motivating households to implement different circular R-strategies such as reduce, reuse, share, repair, and recycle. Our focus is on four key domains: food waste, packaging, textiles, and electronic devices.

CircleUp aims to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and enhance circular economy practices among households in four different countries across Europe: Germany, Latvia, Norway and the United Kingdom. Furthermore, the project wants to foster the social identification of individuals as circular citizens by inviting them to participate in and organise group activities that focus on circular practices that reinforce sustainable social norms and discourage unsustainable habits.

1.2 Methodologies used in CircleUp

To evaluate the effectiveness of the CircleUp tailored intervention package, a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods will be used. This mixed-methods approach allows for a more comprehensive and in-depth understanding of households' behaviour and attitudes towards circular economy practices.

Figure 1 presents the timeline of the different methodology activities that are part of the CircleUp project.

Figure 1. Timeline figure of the CircleUp activities including the survey measurement points.

1.2.1 Quantitative methods

The quantitative methods include online questionnaires and LCA based on information given by the household members. With the questionnaire studies, we aim to capture people's intentions and behaviours, attitudes, emotions, norms and social identities related to the circular economy. More specifically, we focus on four key domains: food waste, packaging, textiles, and electronic devices. Each of these domains represents areas where everyday circular practices can be applied to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and promote the principles of a reduce, reuse, share, repair, and recycle circular economy. The questionnaires will provide insights into the more general attitudes and behaviour of the households. The savings of challenges within the four respective domains will be recorded by users documenting quantities saved by

participating in certain challenges (e.g. food domain: shelf-life extensions or purchases avoided). This data is recorded on i) a household-specific basis, allowing individual savings to be tracked, and ii) a challenge-specific basis, allowing efficiency measurements of certain challenges (e.g. 'Week without food waste'). After having aggregated the different savings of certain challenges, these will be converted into expressive environmental impact indicator such as waste weight (kg) or CO₂ equivalents. Therefore, the questionnaire serves as quantitative input for the life cycle inventory of an LCA and make environmental impacts visible in a targeted manner for the households (preliminary) and for stakeholders of the project (final results). The assessment of environmental impact thus gives us a more detailed reflection on the effect in terms of reducing environmental burden through circular economy practices

1.2.2 Qualitative methods

The qualitative methods include content analysis of the Circular Stories, group discussions and individual interviews with household members. Qualitative data is essential to gain a deeper understanding of the factors influencing people's attitudes and behaviours.

The aim of the Circular Stories content analysis is to explore how participants narrate their engagement in circular practices, how these narratives reflect identity-relevant elements, and the function of emotions in social identity formation related to circular economy. The group discussions will facilitate discussions among the households, allowing them to share their experiences, challenges, and drivers related to circular economy behaviour. The individual interviews will provide an opportunity for more-in depth exploration of the households' thoughts and feelings on the circular economy practices included in the CircleUp intervention package. This approach will help us to identify common themes and patterns, as well as unique insights that may not be captured by the quantitative methods alone.

2 Recruitment questionnaire

2.1 Overall purpose

Within the CircleUp project, we want to recruit 100 households fully participating in the project across four different countries: Germany, Latvia, Norway, and the United Kingdom. This means we need to at least recruit 25 households per country. Since we will ask the households to not only engage in individual but also in collective circular behaviour, ideally within the same neighbourhood, we will recruit households living in the same areas. In addition, we will collaborate closely with community stakeholders such as repair cafes, refill shops, libraries, etc.

Specifically, we will focus on the following regions:

- 25 households in Bergen, Norway
- 25 households in Latvia
- 25 households in Wantage, United Kingdom
- 25 households in Bottrop, Germany

Within the project, we want to include diverse household types in terms of demographics (age, gender, family composition) and socio-economic status (income levels, employment status, education level). Furthermore, we should prioritize households that are not very interested in sustainability to ensure the project benefits those in greatest need. Furthermore, participating households are expected to have access to a smartphone, a basic level of IT competence and a stable internet connection, as these are necessary for participation in the CircleUp project, which will use a digital platform as part of the intervention (for further details, see D2.1).

Households must be motivated and willing to participate in the project for approximately eight months. Furthermore, they need to take part in the CircleUp challenges and writing social circular stories. In every household, we need at least one household member (over 18 years) being responsible for the communication within the household.

The project partners have the autonomy to choose their own recruitment strategies to recruit households, based on their local context and prior experience. They are currently in the recruitment process and will select their preferred recruitment strategies. These strategies may vary and can include methods such as door-to-door visits.

As part of a possible recruitment strategy, a short recruitment questionnaire has been developed to help screen households for a good distribution of different household types. This questionnaire can be used as part of the broader recruitment strategy to recruit households. Additionally, the questionnaire should be adjusted to meet the specific needs of the recruitment strategy that will finally be used by the different project partners. Since this recruitment questionnaire is part of an overall suggested project approach, it can easily be adapted to each pilot country.

Next to some household characteristics as outlined in Table 1, we will collect contact information from the households to be able to contact the households during the project.

The recruitment of the households and the pilot testing of the questionnaires, the interviews and the intervention will take place before the actual launch of the intervention.

Figure 1. Timeline figure of the CircleUp activities including the survey measurement points.

2.2 Stipulated length

It will take maximum 5 minutes to fill in the recruitment questionnaire. The recruitment questionnaire should only be filled in by one person of the household. This will be the person that is in direct contact with the CircleUp team.

2.3 Recruitment questions

Table 1. Questions for the recruitment questionnaire

	Question	Answering alternatives
1	Age	Number from 18 up-over
2	Gender	male/female/other/prefer not to say
3	Household size	Number from 1 up-over
4	How many children in the different age categories live in the household?	Age categories from 0-5/ 6-12/ 12-17
5	Highest level of education and/or some assessment of household income brackets	Follow country standards
6	Type of dwelling / housing	Single house/terraced house/apartment owned/rented
8	<p><u>Circular practices:</u></p> <p>How often do you do the following things in your everyday life:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I use my leftovers • I regularly shop second hand instead of buying new • I make an effort to repair items such as clothes and electronics • I buy products (e.g., food) with as little packaging as possible • I use electronic devices like phones or computers as long as possible before I buy a new one • I am bringing my own containers to a refill shop 	<p>Answering format:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To be honest, I do not care about this and seldom do this • I think it is important, but it is not my top priority, sometimes other things are more important • This is very important for me, so I do it whenever I can
9	<p><u>Environmental identity:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Making pro-environmental choices is an important part of who I am. 	<p>Answering format: Standard agreement scale</p> <p>7-point Likert scale with 1 = completely disagree and 7 = completely agree</p>
10	<p><u>Climate change concern:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I worry about climate change more than other people • I tend to seek out information about climate change in the media (e.g., TV, newspapers, internet) 	<p>Answering format: Standard agreement scale</p> <p>7-point Likert scale with 1 = completely disagree and 7 = completely agree</p>

3 Questionnaires

The next phase of this deliverable describes the development of the questionnaires. The goal of the questionnaires is to gather information from the households and look at changes in current beliefs, attitudes, and behaviours related to circular economy practices. Furthermore, we want to use the questionnaire to measure the effectiveness of the innovative CircleUp intervention package. The questionnaires will be sent to each household member 14 years and older. The questionnaires will be filled in online and will be tested first with the test group.

In total, four questionnaires will be available including the pre-intervention, mid-intervention, post-intervention, and a follow-up. We will only use closed questions for the questionnaires. All the questions drew upon insights from the literature review and the challenges that have been created for the conceptual framework which is described in Deliverable 2.1. The questionnaires will not contain many socio-demographic questions since these will already be asked in the recruitment process for the households before the start of the project. This gives us the opportunity to have more space in the questionnaires itself to ask questions related to the socio-psychological constructs.

The data from the questionnaire data will be analysed by multivariate statistics calculating the intrapersonal differences between the different measurement moments. Figure 1 shows a timeline of the CircleUp activities including the surveys.

Figure 1. Timeline figure of the CircleUp activities including the survey measurement points.

3.1 Pre-intervention

3.1.1 Overall purpose

With the pre-intervention questionnaire, we will identify the baseline measurement of the households' behaviour and attitudes before the start of the tailored CircleUp intervention package.

3.1.2 Stipulated length

To maintain participant engagement in the project and reduce the likelihood of missing data in the survey, the survey length will be limited to a maximum of 25 minutes. This makes it possible to be able to collect the necessary data for analysis while minimizing respondent burden. All household members aged 14 years and older are expected to complete the questionnaire.

3.1.3 Implementation

The pre-test will be filled in online in nettskjema.no.

3.1.4 Questions

The survey questions were developed based on an extensive literature review as outlined in the project's first deliverable (D2.1).

The survey will be tested and refined based on the feedback from project partners during the upcoming project meeting taking place in September 2025. One of the key outcomes of this workshop is to shorten

the length of the survey, thereby minimizing the burden on household members who will be participating in the study.

Table 2. Questions for the quantitative surveys

	Question	Answering alternatives
Socio-demographic information		
1	Participant ID	##### A unique and anonymized 5-digit number to follow up every participant within the household Household### (1-100) Member# (1-9)
2	Age	Number from 14 up-over
3	Gender	male/female/other/prefer not to say
4	Highest level of education and/or some assessment of household income brackets	Follow country standards
5	When you think about your own political views, where would you place yourself on the following scale?	0 – 10 scale with 0 left and 10 right
Socio-psychological constructs measuring individual circular economy attitudes and behaviour		
6	<p>Negative emotions associated with negative consequences: (1 items per domain)</p> <p>-Hearing or reading news about how much food we waste in our society, makes me feel bad</p> <p>-Hearing or reading news about how much single-use packaging we use in our society, makes me feel bad</p> <p>-Hearing or reading news about how many brand new clothes are consumed in our society, makes me feel bad</p> <p>-Hearing or reading news about how many new electronic devices are consumed in our society, makes me feel bad</p>	<p>Answering format: Standard agreement scale</p> <p>7-point Likert scale with 1 = completely disagree and 7 = completely agree</p> <p>Hogg et al., 2021</p> <p>Bamberg, 2013</p> <p>Keller et al., 2021</p>
7	<p>Awareness of consequences/Awareness of need: (2 items per domain)</p> <p>-Reducing food waste helps in solving environmental problems such as climate change, biodiversity loss and pollution</p> <p>-The amount of food we waste in our society is a serious problem</p> <p>-Reducing single-use packaging helps in solving environmental problems such as climate change, biodiversity loss and pollution</p> <p>-The amount of single-use plastic we waste in our society is a serious problem</p>	<p>Answering format: Standard agreement scale</p> <p>7-point Likert scale with 1 = completely disagree and 7 = completely agree</p> <p>Milfont et al., 2015</p> <p>Schwartz, 1977;</p>

	<p>-Reducing the consumption of new electronic devices helps in solving the environmental problems such as climate change, biodiversity loss and pollution</p> <p>-The overconsumption of new electronic devices in our society is a serious problem</p> <p>-Reducing the consumption of new clothes helps in solving the environmental problems such as climate change, biodiversity loss and pollution</p> <p>-The overconsumption of brand-new clothes in our society is a serious problem</p>	<p>Schwartz and Howard, 1981</p> <p>Klöckner and Blöbaum, 2010</p> <p>Bamberg, 2013</p> <p>Keller et al., 2021</p>
8	<p>Perceived behavioural control (2 items per domain)</p> <p>-How much control do you think you have in reducing your food waste during the next months?</p> <p>-How easy or difficult would it be for you to reduce your food waste?</p> <p>-How much control do you think you have in reducing your single-use packaging during the next months?</p> <p>-How easy or difficult would it be for you to reduce your single-use packaging?</p> <p>-How much control do you think you have in reducing buying brand new clothes during the next months?</p> <p>-How easy or difficult would it be for you to reduce buying brand new clothes?</p> <p>-How much control do you think you have in reducing buying new electronic devices during the next months?</p> <p>-How easy or difficult would it be for you to reduce buying new electronic devices?</p>	<p>Answering format: Standard agreement scale</p> <p>5-point Likert scale with 1 = very difficult and 5 = very easy</p> <p>5-point Likert scale with 1= very much control and 5 = very little control</p> <p>Bamberg, 2013</p> <p>Ajzen, 1991</p> <p>Russell et al., 2017</p>
9	<p>Perceived own responsibility: (2 items per domain)</p> <p>-It is my duty to reduce food waste</p> <p>-I feel personally responsible to reduce food waste</p> <p>-It is my duty to reduce single-use packaging</p> <p>-I feel personally responsible to reduce single-use packaging</p> <p>-It is my duty to reduce buying brand new clothes</p> <p>-I feel personally responsible to reduce buying brand new clothes</p> <p>-It is my duty to reduce buying new electronic devices</p> <p>-I feel personally responsible to reduce buying new electronic devices</p>	<p>Answering format: Standard agreement scale</p> <p>7-point Likert scale with 1 = completely disagree and 7 = completely agree</p> <p>Bamberg, 2013</p> <p>Swartz, 1977</p> <p>Abrahamse and Steg, 2009</p> <p>Keller et al., 2021</p>

10	<p>Positive emotions anticipated with goal achievement: (1 item per domain)</p> <p>-If I can reduce my food waste in the following months, I will feel happy</p> <p>-If I can reduce my single-use packaging in the following months, I will feel happy</p> <p>-If I can reduce buying new electronic devices in the following months, I will feel happy</p> <p>-If I can reduce buying brand new clothes in the following months, I will feel happy</p>	<p>Answering format: Standard agreement scale</p> <p>7-point Likert scale with 1 = completely disagree and 7 = completely agree</p> <p>Bamberg, 2013</p> <p>Koenig-Lewis et al., 2014</p> <p>Sunio et al., 2018</p>
11	<p>Attitudes: (2 items per domain)</p> <p>-Wasting food feels</p> <p>-Reducing my food waste would work ...</p> <p>-Using single-use packaging feels ...</p> <p>-Reducing my single-use packaging would work ...</p> <p>-Buying brand new clothes regularly feels</p> <p>-Reducing buying brand new clothes would work ...</p> <p>-Buying new electronic devices regularly feels</p> <p>-Reducing buying new electronic devices would work ...</p>	<p>Answering format: Standard agreement scale</p> <p>5-point Likert scale with 1 =very bad and 5 = very good)</p> <p>Ajzen, 2001</p> <p>Ajzen, 1991</p> <p>Fishbein and Ajzen, 2011</p> <p>Bamberg, 2013</p> <p>Olsson et al., 2018</p> <p>Instrumental and affective dimensions</p>
12	<p>Social norms: 2 items per domain</p> <p>-People who are important to me reduce their food waste</p> <p>-People who are important to me think it is good to reduce food waste</p>	<p>Answering format: Standard agreement scale</p> <p>7-point Likert scale with 1 = completely disagree and 7 = completely agree</p>

	<p>-People who are important to me reduce buying single-use packaging</p> <p>-People who are important to me think it is good to avoid single-use packaging</p> <p>-People who are important to me reduce buying new electronic devices</p> <p>-People who are important to me think it is good to reduce buying new electronic devices</p> <p>-People who are important to me reduce buying brand new clothes</p> <p>-People who are important to me think it is good to reduce buying brand new clothes</p>	<p>Smith et al. 2012 Descriptive and injunctive norms</p> <p>Ajzen, 1991</p> <p>Ajzen and Fishbein, 1980</p> <p>Bamberg, 2013</p> <p>Olsson et al., 2018</p>
13	<p>Personal norms: 2 items per domain</p> <p>-Because of my own values and beliefs, I don't want to waste food</p> <p>-It is important for me to reduce wasting food</p> <p>-Because of my own values and beliefs, I don't want to buy single-use packaging</p> <p>-It is important for me to reduce single-use packaging</p> <p>-Because of my own values and beliefs, I don't want to buy new electronic devices too often</p> <p>-It is important for me to reduce buying electronic devices</p> <p>-Because of my own values and beliefs, I don't want to buy brand new clothes too often</p> <p>-It is important for me to reduce buying brand new clothes</p>	<p>Answering format: Standard agreement scale</p> <p>7-point Likert scale with 1 = completely disagree and 7 = completely agree</p> <p>Schwartz, 1977; Schwartz and Howard, 1981</p> <p>Bamberg, 2013</p> <p>Olsson et al., 2018</p>
14	<p>Habits (2 items per domain)</p> <p>-Throwing away my leftovers is something I do without much thinking</p> <p>-It is part of my routine to throw away my leftovers</p> <p>-Buying food in single-use packaging is something I do without much thinking</p> <p>-It is part of my routine that I buy food packed in single-use packaging</p> <p>-It is part of my routine to buy brand new clothes whenever I want something new</p> <p>-Buying brand new clothes is something I do without much thinking</p>	<p>Answering format: Standard agreement scale</p> <p>7-point Likert scale with 1 = completely disagree and 7 = completely agree</p> <p>Verplanken, 2006</p> <p>Kurz et al., 2015</p> <p>Whitmarsh et al., 2018</p> <p>Stern, 2000</p>

	<p>-It is part of my routine to buy new electronic devices (tools, gadgets) whenever I want something new</p> <p>-Buying new electronic devices (tools, gadgets) is something I do without much thinking</p>	
15	<p>Material Values</p> <p>- I admire people who own expensive electronic devices and clothes</p> <p>-The things I own say a lot about how well I'm doing in life</p> <p>-Buying things gives me a lot of pleasure</p> <p>-I like to have a lot of luxury in my life</p> <p>- My life would be better if I owned certain things that I don't have</p> <p>-I would be happier if I could afford to buy more things</p> <p>-I usually buy only the things I need</p> <p>-I try to keep my life simple, as far as possessions are concerned</p> <p>-The things I own aren't all that important to me</p>	<p>answering format: Standard agreement scale</p> <p>7-point Likert scale with 1 = completely disagree and 7 = completely agree</p> <p>Scale adopted from Richins (2004); Akbar et al., 2016, Camacho-Otero et al. 2019</p>
16	<p>Product Retention Tendency</p> <p>-Getting rid of stuff is difficult for me.</p> <p>-I tend to hold on to my possessions.</p> <p>-Unless I have a really good reason to throw something away, I keep it.</p> <p>-I do not like to dispose of possessions.</p>	<p>Answering format: Standard agreement scale</p> <p>7-point Likert scale with 1 = completely disagree and 7 = completely agree</p> <p>Scale adopted from Haws et al. 2012;</p> <p>Gomes et al. 2022, Camacho-Otero et al. 2019, Akbar et al., 2016</p>
17	<p>Behaviour: FOOD</p> <p>-I use a meal plan to organize my meals accordingly</p> <p>-I use a shopping list when I go shopping and stick to it</p> <p>-I make a leftovers meal with my leftovers</p> <p>-I have a good overview of the stocks of food in my freezer, fridge, and cupboards</p> <p>-I have a good overview of the stocks of leftovers in my freezer and fridge</p> <p>-My food in the freezer, fridge, and cupboards is stored properly</p> <p>-My leftovers in the freezer and fridge are stored properly</p>	<p>Answering format:</p> <p>Agreement scale 5-point Likert scale with 1= never, 2=rarely, 3=sometimes, 4=often, 5=always or whenever possible</p> <p>Schmidt and Matthies, 2018</p>

	<p>-I am confused by the best before and use by dates on food products</p> <p>-I rely on my senses, such as smell or taste, to check whether food is still edible</p> <p>-When I go grocery shopping, I buy more than I actually need</p> <p>-I immediately throw away food which has passed the best before date, although still edible</p> <p>-I make impulsive purchases due to promising or attractive discounts in supermarkets</p> <p>-I choose oddly shaped produce when shopping</p> <p>-I buy discounted products that are close to their expiration date</p>	
18	<p>Behaviour: PACKAGING</p> <p>-When I order a take-away drink in a cafe, I take my own reusable cup with me</p> <p>-When I order take-away food in a restaurant, I take my own take-way food container with me</p> <p>-I avoid buying single-use packaging-I take my own bag to the supermarket instead of buying single-use bags</p> <p>-I avoid using thin, single-use plastic bags for fruit and vegetables when shopping at the supermarket</p> <p>-I use reusable bags when shopping</p> <p>-I use reusable containers to fill when purchasing food in supermarkets</p> <p>-I bring my lunch to work in a reusable lunch box</p> <p>-I buy food products in zero-packaging stores</p>	<p>Answering format:</p> <p>agreement scale 5-point Likert scale with 1= never, 2=rarely, 3=sometimes, 4=often, 5=always or whenever possible</p> <p>Keller et al., 2021</p> <p>Poortinga et al., 2013</p> <p>Du Rietz and Kremel, 2023</p>
19	<p>Behaviour: ELECTRONIC DEVICES</p> <p>-I buy secondhand electronic devices</p> <p>-I repair my electronic devices that are broken (by myself or by professionals)</p> <p>-I give away electronic devices to others which I don't need</p> <p>-I store broken electronic devices at home</p> <p>-I take care of my electronic devices</p>	<p>Answering format:</p> <p>agreement scale 5-point Likert scale with 1= never, 2=rarely, 3=sometimes, 4=often, 5=always or whenever possible</p> <p>Bovea et al., 2017</p>
20	<p>Behaviour: TEXTILES</p>	<p>Answering format:</p> <p>agreement scale 5-point Likert scale with 1= never,</p>

	<p>-I buy secondhand clothes</p> <p>-I try to minimize my wardrobe</p> <p>-I try to avoid buying new clothes</p> <p>-I repair my damaged clothes (by myself or by professionals)</p>	<p>2=rarely, 3=sometimes, 4=often, 5=always or whenever possible</p> <p>Vesterinen and Syrjälä, 2022</p> <p>Becker-Leifhold, 2018</p> <p>Borusiak et al., 2020</p>
21	<p>Behavioural intention: 2 item per domain</p> <p>During the next months...</p> <p>how willing are you to reduce your food waste?</p> <p>how willing are you to reduce your single-use packaging?</p> <p>how willing are you to reduce buying brand new clothes?</p> <p>how willing are you to reduce buying new electronic devices?</p> <p>During the next months, I am planning to ...</p> <p>...reduce my food waste</p> <p>...reduce my single-use packaging</p> <p>...reduce buying brand new clothes</p> <p>...reduce buying new electronic devices</p>	<p>Answering format: Standard agreement scale</p> <p>(very willing – not willing at all)</p> <p>+</p> <p>(1=completely disagree and 7=completely agree)</p> <p>Bamberg, 2013</p>
<p>Items measuring collective circular behaviour and attitudes: The items are also based on the social identity model of pro-environmental action SIMPEA, Fritsche et al., 2018)</p>		
22	<p>Awareness of consequences/awareness of needs (1 item per domain)</p> <p>-Reducing food waste together with the other CircleUp members helps in solving environmental problems such as climate change, biodiversity loss and pollution</p> <p>-Reducing single-use packaging together with the other CircleUp members helps in solving the environmental problems such as climate change, biodiversity loss and pollution</p> <p>-Reducing buying new electronic devices together with the other CircleUp members helps in solving environmental problems such as climate change, biodiversity loss and pollution</p> <p>-Reducing buying brand new clothes together with the other CircleUp members helps in solving environmental problems such as climate change, biodiversity loss and pollution</p>	<p>Answering format: Standard agreement scale</p> <p>7-point Likert scale with 1 = completely disagree and 7 = completely agree</p> <p>Milfont et al., 2015</p> <p>Schwartz, 1977;</p> <p>Schwartz and Howard, 1981</p> <p>Klößner and Blöbaum, 2010</p> <p>Bamberg, 2013</p>
23	<p>Perceived responsibility (1 items)</p>	<p>Answering format: Standard agreement scale</p>

	<p>-It is our duty as CircleUp members to reduce food waste together</p> <p>-It is our duty as CircleUp members to reduce single-use packaging together</p> <p>-It is our duty as CircleUp members to reduce buying new electronic devices together</p> <p>-It is our duty as CircleUp members to reduce buying brand new clothes together</p>	<p>7-point Likert scale with 1 = completely disagree and 7 = completely agree</p> <p>Bamberg, 2013</p> <p>Schwartz, 1977</p> <p>Abrahamse and Steg, 2009</p>
24	<p>Social positive emotions: 1 item per domain</p> <p>-If we as CircleUp members can reduce our food waste in the following months, I will feel happy</p> <p>-If we as CircleUp members can reduce our single-use packaging in the following months, I will feel happy</p> <p>-If we as CircleUp members can reduce buying electronic devices in the following months, I will feel happy</p> <p>-If we as CircleUp members can reduce buying clothes in the following months, I will feel happy</p>	<p>Answering format: Standard agreement scale</p> <p>7-point Likert scale with 1 = completely disagree and 7 = completely agree</p> <p>Bamberg, 2013</p> <p>Koenig-Lewis et al., 2014</p> <p>Sunio et al., 2018</p>
25	<p>Behavioural intentions for collective action</p> <p>During the next months,</p> <p>how willing are you to reduce your food waste together with the CircleUp members?</p> <p>how willing are you to reduce your single-use packaging together with the CircleUp members?</p> <p>how willing are you to reduce buying new electronic devices together with the CircleUp members?</p> <p>how willing are you to reduce buying brand new clothes together with the CircleUp members?</p> <p>During the next months, I am planning together with the other CircleUp members to ...</p> <p>...reduce food waste</p> <p>...reduce single-use packaging</p> <p>...reduce buying brand new clothes</p> <p>...reduce buying new electronic devices</p>	<p>Answering format: Standard agreement scale</p> <p>5-point Likert scale with 1 = very willing and 5 = not willing at all</p> <p>Bamberg, 2013</p>

26	<p>Attitudes towards collective action</p> <p>-Reducing food waste together with other CircleUp members feels</p> <p>-Reducing single-use packaging together with other CircleUp members feels</p> <p>-Reducing buying brand new clothes with other CircleUp members feels ...</p> <p>-Reducing buying new electronic devices with other CircleUp members feels ...</p>	<p>Answering format: Standard agreement scale</p> <p>5-point Likert scale with 1 =very bad and 5 = very good</p> <p>Ajzen, 2001 Instrumental and affective dimensions</p>
27	<p>Social norms towards collective action-CircleUp members think it is good to reduce food waste</p> <p>-CircleUp members reduce food waste</p> <p>-CircleUp members think it is good to reduce single-use packaging</p> <p>-CircleUp members reduce single-use packaging</p> <p>-CircleUp members think it is good to reduce buying brand new clothes</p> <p>-CircleUp members reduce buying brand new clothes</p> <p>-CircleUp members think it is good to reduce buying new electronic devices</p> <p>-CircleUp members reduce buying new electronic devices</p>	<p>Answering format: Standard agreement scale</p> <p>7-point Likert scale with 1 = completely disagree and 7 = completely agree</p> <p>Smith et al. 2012 Descriptive and injunctive</p>
28	<p>Personal norms towards collective action (1 item per domain)</p> <p>I feel an obligation for us as CircleUp members to reduce food waste</p> <p>I feel an obligation for us as CircleUp members to reduce plastic packaging</p> <p>I feel an obligation for us as CircleUp members to reduce buying new electronic devices</p> <p>I feel an obligation for us as CircleUp members to reduce buying brand new clothes</p>	<p>Answering format: Standard agreement scale</p> <p>7-point Likert scale with 1 = completely disagree and 7 = completely agree</p>
29	<p>Perceived behavioural control towards collective action</p> <p>-How much control do you think you have as CircleUp members in reducing food waste together?</p> <p>-How much control do you think you have as CircleUp members in reducing single-use packaging together?</p>	<p>Answering format: Standard agreement scale</p> <p>5-point Likert scale with 1 = very difficult and 5 = very easy</p> <p>5-point Likert scale with 1= very much control and 5 = very little control</p>

	<p>-How much control do you think you have as CircleUp members in reducing buying brand new clothes together?</p> <p>-How much control do you think you have as CircleUp members in reducing buying new electronic devices?</p>	<p>Bamberg, 2013</p> <p>Ajzen, 1991</p> <p>Russell et al., 2017</p>
30	<p>Negative emotions</p> <p>Not for the collective level</p>	
31	<p>Ingroup identification - CircleUp members</p> <p>[Solidarity]</p> <p>I feel a bond with other CircleUp members.</p> <p>I feel committed to the CircleUp project.</p> <p>[Satisfaction]</p> <p>I think that CircleUp members have a lot to be proud of.</p> <p>Being a CircleUp member gives me a good feeling.</p> <p>[Centrality]</p> <p>I often think about the fact that I am a CircleUp member.</p> <p>The fact that I am a CircleUp member is an important part of my identity.</p> <p>Being a CircleUp member is an important part of how I see myself.</p> <p>[Individual Self-Stereotyping]</p> <p>I have a lot in common with the average CircleUp member.</p> <p>I am similar to the average CircleUp member.</p> <p>[In-Group Homogeneity]</p> <p>CircleUp members have a lot in common with each other.</p> <p>CircleUp members are very similar to each other.</p>	<p>Answering format: Standard agreement scale</p> <p>7-point Likert scale with 1 = completely disagree and 7 = completely agree</p> <p>Leach et al. 2008</p>

	<p>Ingroup identification – Circular Citizen</p> <p>A "Circular Citizen" is someone who actively supports and puts into practice the principles of the circular economy. This means reducing waste, for example by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • using products as long as possible, • question the need of buying new products, • repairing instead of discarding, • sharing resources • and recycling whenever possible. <p>"Circular Citizens" feel responsible for creating a sustainable future. They advocate for a society that values resources and keeps them in use, rather than wasting them.</p> <p>Please consider the definition above when answering the following questions. We are interested in how much you identify with being a "Circular Citizen" based on this understanding. Please indicate your agreement with each statement.</p> <p>I feel a bond with people whom I consider to be circular citizens.</p> <p>The idea of being a Circular Citizen gives me a good feeling.</p> <p>Being a Circular Citizen is an important part of how I see myself.</p>	<p>Answering format: Standard agreement scale</p> <p>7-point Likert scale with 1 = completely disagree and 7 = completely agree</p> <p>Leach et al. (2008), adapted to Circular Citizen identity and shortened (originally a 14 item scale)</p>
32	<p>Ingroup identification – Neighbourhood</p> <p>Please answer the following questions thinking about the area immediately around your home that you consider your local neighbourhood. This might be your street, your block, or a small cluster of streets that you feel are part of your immediate community.</p> <p>I feel a bond with people in my neighbourhood.</p> <p>Being a resident of my neighbourhood gives me a good feeling.</p> <p>Being a resident of my neighbourhood is an important part of how I see myself.</p>	<p>Answering format: Standard agreement scale</p> <p>-7-point Likert scale with 1 = completely disagree and 7 = completely agree</p> <p>Leach et al. (2008), adapted to Circular Citizen identity and shortened (originally a 14 item scale)</p>
33	<p>Global human identification</p> <p>I see myself as a global citizen</p>	<p>Answering format: Standard agreement scale</p>

	<p>I can identify with the slogan 'we are all humans of one world'</p> <p>I feel connected with the whole earth</p> <p>I feel part of the earth</p>	<p>-7-point Likert scale with 1 = completely disagree and 7 = completely agree</p> <p>Renger & Reese (2017)</p>
34	<p>Citizenship behaviours towards systemic change</p> <p><i>Please tell us if and how often you have done these actions in the last 12 months.</i></p> <p><i>[Adaption for second, third and fourth wave]</i></p> <p><i>Please tell us if and how often you have been doing these actions since the last survey (approximately X months ago).</i></p> <p>In my role at work or another organisation, I have promoted the adoption of circular goods and services.</p> <p>I have contributed ideas or feedback to companies on how to make their products or services more circular.</p> <p>I have volunteered for organisations that promote circular economy initiatives.</p> <p>I have supported or helped create initiatives like tool libraries, repair cafés, or sharing schemes in my community.</p> <p>I discuss circular economy issues with friends, family, or colleagues to raise awareness.</p> <p>I encourage people around me to change their consumption habits in line with circular economy principles.</p>	<p>Answering format: Standard agreement scale</p> <p>Beatrice: 5-point Likert scale with 1=never, 2=rarely, 3=sometimes, 4=often, 5=always or whenever possible</p> <p>Self-generated items based on SCCA framework from Pacheco, van der Werft & Steg 2025</p>
35	<p>Responsibility towards collective action</p> <p>It is the responsibility of everyone in CircleUp to reduce food waste</p> <p>It is the responsibility of everyone in CircleUp to reduce single-use packaging</p> <p>It is the responsibility of everyone in CircleUp to reduce buying brand new clothes</p> <p>It is the responsibility of everyone in CircleUp to reduce buying new electronic devices</p>	<p>Answering format: Standard agreement scale</p> <p>7-point Likert scale with 1 = completely disagree and 7 = completely agree</p> <p>Bamberg, 2013</p> <p>Swartz, 1977</p> <p>Abrahamse and Steg, 2009</p> <p>Keller et al., 2021</p>
36	<p>Collective efficacy</p> <p>-All together as CircleUp members, we can make it possible to reduce food waste</p> <p>-All together as CircleUp members, we can make it possible to reduce single-use packaging</p> <p>-All together as CircleUp members, we can make it possible to reduce buying brand new clothes</p>	<p>Answering format: Standard agreement scale</p> <p>7-point Likert scale with 1 = completely disagree and 7 = completely agree</p> <p>van Zomeren et al. (2008, 2010)</p> <p>Bandura, 2000</p>

	-All together as CircleUp members, we can make it possible to reduce brand new clothes	
37	<p>Behaviour FOOD</p> <p>-I am organizing leftover dinners</p> <p>-I am organizing leftover dinners with other CircleUp members</p> <p>-I am organizing events on reducing food waste</p> <p>-I am organizing events on reducing food waste with other CircleUp members</p>	<p>Answering format:</p> <p>Agreement scale 5-point Likert scale with 1= never, 2=rarely, 3=sometimes, 4=often, 5=always or whenever possible</p>
38	<p>Behaviour PACKAGING</p> <p>-I am buying in bulk together with others</p> <p>-I am buying in bulk together with other CircleUp members</p>	<p>Answering format:</p> <p>Agreement scale: 5-point Likert scale with 1= never, 2=rarely, 3=sometimes, 4=often, 5=always or whenever possible</p>
39	<p>Behaviour ELECTRONIC DEVICES</p> <p>-I share electronic devices with others</p> <p>-I share electronic devices with other CircleUp members</p> <p>-I am organizing an electronic repair cafe with others</p> <p>-I am organizing an electronic repair café with other CircleUp members</p>	<p>Answering format:</p> <p>Agreement scale 5-point Likert scale with 1= never, 2=rarely, 3=sometimes, 4=often, 5=always or whenever possible</p>
40	<p>Behaviour TEXTILES</p> <p>-I share or swap my clothes with others</p> <p>-I share or swap my clothes with other CircleUp members</p> <p>-I am organizing a clothing swap, upcycle, or repair event together with others</p> <p>-I am organizing a clothing swap, upcycle, or repair event together with other CircleUp members</p>	<p>Answering format:</p> <p>Agreement scale 5-point Likert scale with 1= never, 2=rarely, 3=sometimes, 4=often, 5=always or whenever possible</p>

3.2 Other interventions

After the 1st intervention phase of the project (1st survey), a mid-test questionnaire (2nd survey) will be taken to assess the effectiveness of the intervention package and will determine if any adjustments are needed.

The mid-test is meant to capture changes from the baseline to the mid-term. To be able to measure differences between people’s attitudes and behaviour, the same questions as the pre-test will be asked.

The post-test questionnaire (3rd survey) is meant to capture changes from the baseline to after all interventions. The same questions as the pre-and the mid-test will be asked. The final step would involve taking a post-measurement to assess the impact of the interventions and changes made. Again, the same questions as the pre-test and mid-test will be asked.

At the end of the CircleUp project (M42), we will organize a follow-up questionnaire (final survey). The follow-up questionnaire is meant to capture long term effects of all interventions used in the project. The same questions as the pre-test, mid-test, and post-test will be asked for the follow-up questionnaire.

Figure 1 shows the timeline of the four different survey interventions.

Figure 1. Timeline figure of the CircleUp activities including the survey measurement points.

4 LCA

With the LCA we want to gather a brief instant feedback in terms of material flows reduced due to the challenges tested. As part of the challenges, participants can use the digital tool to enter the savings they were able to achieve in the following domains as a result of the respective challenge: (1) textiles: buying or redistributing (online/stationary, new/second-hand, total amount of clothes) repairing activities (self/commercial), (2) food: choices , management and practices cooking activities, managing leftovers, food waste), (3) packaging: buying unpacked products and using reusable containers, refilling packaging, disposable coffee cups and lunch boxes, (4) electronics: buying or redistributing, sharing, and repairing activities.

The LCA approach as part of the assessment will be divided into two parts. First, the savings potential of the households must be tracked (i), and second, the impact of the respective savings of a specific saved product unit must be assessed (ii). The reduced environmental impact for each product is calculated from the impact factor per product unit and the number of product units saved. The reduced environmental impact of the respective challenge is the sum of all reduced environmental impacts of the products.

i) As part of each individual challenge, households are given the mandatory task of reporting their realised savings potential in the app. All material (and energy) flows saved have to be specified and quantified. Using the food domain as an example, it is intended for the households to be able to say which amount of a certain food could be reduced within a certain challenge. Households can enter their savings for each challenge separately via the app. There are lists of all product items, which are used to enter the type and

quantity of the savings. The lists are available to households for the entire duration of the challenge and can therefore be filled in according to households' individual needs.

ii) To determine the environmental impact of the savings, LCAs are created for each product type and the results are stored in the app. Characterisation factors are used to calculate the contribution of each individual product type to the respective environmental impact of the challenge - e.g. how much global warming potential a particular product unit has (in CO₂-eq). The contributions of all savings are then aggregated to obtain an overall picture of the environmental impact saved.

Since this self-reported data could be incomplete and biased, it is compared - where possible - with data from the automated waste data analysis and checked for plausibility. Nevertheless, the data from the waste bins is not included in the calculations as it does not differentiate sufficiently between the different types of waste generated and respectively the products saved.

Table 3. Questions for the LCA studies

FOOD		
Behaviour: Plan purchases to avoid food waste **this behaviour will be tested, whether it is possible to gather data for LCA in the pretest**	1. In the course of the challenge, I reduced my food purchases by planning. Compared to my ordinary purchases, I bought fewer of the following products.	Answering format: Households can select from a list the foods to which the above questions apply. Households select the type of food saved and quantify the amount saved. The list will be available to households for the duration of the entire challenge and can be edited and supplemented at any time. Households can therefore determine the frequency of visits themselves. If no entries are made, warnings are sent at regular intervals.
Behaviour: Reuse leftovers	1. In the course of the challenge, I reused the leftover food that I would otherwise have thrown away	see the answering format above
Behaviour: Give away leftovers	1. In the course of the challenge, I passed on the following foods to my friends, neighbours and XY. 2. In the course of the challenge, I received the following foods from my friends, neighbours and XY.	see the answering format above
Behaviour: share leftover management skills with others		
TEXTILES		
Behaviour: reduce textiles	1. In the course of the challenge, I have decided not to buy excessive amounts of clothing. this has prevented me from buying the following clothes	Households can select from a list the types of textiles to which the above questions apply. Households select the type of textiles saved and quantify the amount saved. The list will be available to households for the duration of the entire challenge and can be edited and supplemented at

		any time. Households can therefore determine the frequency of visits themselves. If no entries are made, warnings are sent at regular intervals.
Behaviour: Buy second hand clothes	1. In the course of the challenge, I have bought secondhand clothes instead of brand-new ones	see the answering format above
Behaviour: Reuse, repair, upcycle clothes	1. In the course of the challenge, I have repaired a clothing item that was damaged	see the answering format above
PACKAGING		
Behaviour: Avoid packaging	.In the course of the challenge, I have taken my own reusable bag with me and therefore saved the following packagings.	Households can select from a list of packaging items to which the above questions apply. Households select the type of food saved and quantify the amount saved. The list will be available to households for the duration of the entire challenge and can be edited and supplemented at any time. Households can therefore determine the frequency of visits themselves. If no entries are made, warnings are sent at regular intervals.
Behaviour: Reuse packaging	1. In the course of the challenge, ... I have avoided single-use packaging by reusing packagings previously bought and still acceptable to be used	see the answering format above
Behaviour: Avoid packaging together	1. In the course of the challenge, I have taken my reusable own container with me to buy in bulk	see the answering format above
ELECTRONICS		
Behaviour: Reduce buying electronics	1. In the course of the challenge, I didn't buy the following electrical devices as I was sharing it with other households in the course of a professional sharing service model or private lending 2. In the course of the challenge, I have given an electronic device to someone else	Households can select from a list of electronics to which the above questions apply. Households select the type of electronics that apply to the respective challenge. The list will be available to households for the duration of the entire challenge and can be edited and supplemented at any time. Households can therefore determine the frequency of visits themselves. If no entries are made, warnings are sent at regular intervals.
Behaviour: broken electronics	In the course of the challenge I have repaired the following electrical device. (if so, it would be nice to specify which part of the device wasn't working anymore and had to be replaced.	see the answering format above + additionally list of electrical device parts that had to be replaced

Behaviour: Reuse electronics	In the course of the challenge I have bought the following second-hand electronic device instead of a new one	see the answering format above
Behaviour: share electronics	During the last month ... I have shared an electronic device with someone else If yes, using an online platform or with someone I know	Answering format: see the answering format above

5 Circular stories evaluation

As outlined in Deliverable 2.1, the “Circular Story” is the core narrative element in the CircleUp’s community building concept. Storytelling serves as a participatory approach that invites individuals to reflect on cognitive and behavioural changes and to share personal experiences of circular practices, such as repairing, reusing, or buying second-hand. These narratives, collected and exchanged on the digital platform, act as both creative and educational tools. They potentially strengthen individual engagement with circular practices while fostering a shared social identity and collective learning within the community.

To assess the effectiveness and impact of the Circular Stories component, a mixed-methods evaluation approach will be employed, combining both qualitative and quantitative methods. This will allow for a comprehensive understanding of how storytelling contributes to engagement with circular practices and identity formation as a Circular Citizen.

1. Content Analysis of Stories

All submitted Circular Stories will be systematically analysed using qualitative content analysis. The aim is to identify:

- The types of circular behaviours described (e.g. reuse, repair, sharing),
- The extent to which these behaviours were carried out in a collaborative manner, involving real-world interactions with people – whether CircleUp members or friends and family,
- The emotional tone of the stories (e.g. pride, satisfaction, frustration),
- Language indicating identity positioning (e.g. "I felt like I was doing the right thing", "part of something bigger", use of the pronoun "we" as identity marker).

If participants have uploaded pictures, these will be also taken into account for the qualitative analysis.

2. Engagement metrics (digital platform)

For stories submitted via the digital platform, metrics will be analysed to track user interaction:

- Number of stories submitted,
- Length of stories,
- Frequency of views, likes, and comments,
- Patterns of engagement over time.

These indicators will offer insights into individual engagement, social recognition, feedback dynamics, and overall platform use.

3. Emotion journaling

As a complementary feature to the Circular Stories, the digital platform includes an emotion journaling component, designed to capture participants’ emotional responses throughout the behavioural change process through emojis, an associated feeling selected by the user, and a short note why they felt like this.

D2.2: Methodology development for assessing the psychological and behavioural effects of the intervention

The journaling data offers insights into the affective dimension of behaviour change processes toward circular economy.

To evaluate the emotion journaling component, the following methods will be applied:

- Thematic analysis of journal entries: A qualitative analysis of selected emotion entries will be conducted to identify recurring themes, emotional trajectories, and reflections linked to identity and behaviour.
- Quantitative Monitoring: Frequency and consistency of journaling (e.g. number of entries per participant, across stages) will be tracked to assess user engagement and identify drop-off points.
- Follow-up interviews: To understand the perceived usefulness and emotional impact of the journaling practice, selected participants will be invited to answer additional questions in the qualitative interviews.

4. Triangulation with survey data, group discussions and interviews

To strengthen the validity of findings, results from the content analysis of the stories will be triangulated with data from the quantitative survey, group discussions, and interviews. From the quantitative surveys, aggregated values from selected constructs in the survey, particularly measures of ingroup identification, will be considered to complement and contextualise the qualitative insights.

To gain deeper insights into participants' experiences, semi-structured interviews and group discussion contain story related questions. Key topics include:

- Motivation to share a story,
- Perceived impact of stories,
- Feelings of belonging or identity development,
- Suggestions for improvement.

Thematic analysis will be used to interpret the data and triangulate findings from other methods.

6 Group discussion

6.1 Overall purpose

The hierarchical principles of a circular economy prioritise reducing, reusing and repairing over recycling. These R-strategies aim to extend the lifespan of products and reduce the overall waste. However, current research conducted shows that these practices are not yet widely embraced (Bovea et al., 2018). Therefore, through group discussions, we aim to gain a better understanding of people's experiences, attitudes, and behaviour towards important circular economy practices such as sharing items with others (i.e., friends, family, neighbours) and repairing products (e.g., clothing items and electronic devices). We explore practices in the context of sharing and repairing which involves either self-repair or professional repair services. Additionally, the interviews will focus on maintaining clothes and electronic devices.

Households are important stakeholders in a circular economy society, not only as consumers but also as active citizens being part of a community and a neighbourhood they belong to. Therefore, we also want to investigate the importance of the community for households within these circular practices. We want to look beyond the close relationships (e.g. friends and family) and also include neighbours as important in the social context of households for being involved in circular economy practices such as reuse and repair practices.

Within CircleUp, writing circular stories is an important part of the CircleUp intervention. After each challenge, people will reflect on their circular practices they engaged in and will create a story on the online CircleUp platform. We want to look at whether households can be engaged towards circular economy practices by the practice of storytelling. Does the storytelling help in fostering a sense of a circular citizen?

6.2 Interview guide and procedures

The questions that are part of the interview guideline can be found in Table 4. Although we will use semi-structured interviews, it is important to have some flexibility for the questions. The interview guide should be tailored to the specific context of the country. The group discussion will be conducted while we are actively working with the households.

The group discussion should not last for more than one hour and can be conducted with 5-10 different household members 14 years and older. The interview guide will be tested with the test group. All the interviews will be audio-recorded to ensure accuracy for the analysis afterwards. Furthermore, all data from the different group interviews will be automatically transcribed and translated to English language to ensure accuracy of the interview analysis. We will recruit household members for four different group discussions (one per country).

Based on the interview data, we will identify codes and categories relevant to the concept described above and advance our understanding of performing circular practices which are important for households in a circular economy society.

Table 4. Interview guidelines for the group discussions

General questions Circular economy	<p>When you hear the world circular economy, what comes to your mind?</p> <p>What is circular economy for you?</p> <p>How important do you think it is to engage in circular economy practices such as reducing, reusing, repairing, or recycling?</p> <p>Which circular economy facilities are you familiar with?</p> <p>Which circular economy practices are you currently applying?</p> <p>What motivates you to participate in circular economy practices?</p>
Circular practices on the collective level	<p>Do you share or swap clothes with others? With whom?</p> <p>Do you share electronic devices with others? With whom?</p> <p>Do you repair clothes or electronic devices? Why (not)?</p> <p>Do you think it is worth the effort to maintain, share and repair items such as clothes and electronic devices?</p> <p>Do you take care of your clothes and electronic devices to last longer? How?</p> <p>Which tools would you like/not like to share with others? Such as garden tools, toys, clothes, bikes, cars</p> <p>Do you think second-hand and sharing, rental fashion is the future?</p> <p>What could make sharing and repairing solutions easier for you?</p> <p>Importance of ownership (clothes and electronic devices)</p>

<p>The role of the community/neighbourhood for circular economy practices</p>	<p>Do you feel a sense of community in your neighbourhood? How? Why?</p> <p>How important is your community/your neighbours in supporting sharing and repairing practices?</p> <p>Do you have sharing or rental organisations in your neighbourhood?</p> <p>Can you give some examples of how your community, or your neighbourhood has influenced your reuse and repair practices?</p> <p>What makes it easy/difficult to participate in circular economy activities such as sharing in your community/neighbourhood?</p> <p>How do you feel about organizing an activity with other people such as a repair café, a leftover dinner.</p> <p>How can (non)existing community initiatives enhance your participation in circular economy practices such as reuse or repair?</p> <p>What changes would you like to see in your neighbourhood when thinking about a circular society?</p>
<p>The role of the family (socialization processes)</p> <p>Try to gain insights into how the circular economy practices are adopted, shared, and reinforced among the household members.</p>	<p>Do you discuss circular economy practices within the family?</p> <p>Do you try to influence other household members with regard to circular economy practices? Food preparation, preparing food, food planning, taking care of electronic devices, repairing clothes or electronic devices,...</p> <p>Households with children: Have you learned some practices from your parents? Have you learned some practices from your children?</p> <p>Are there any circular economy practices that you do together as a household? (e.g., meal planning, second-hand shopping, repairing clothes or electronic devices, DIY)</p> <p>Do you make the decision together whether or not you plan to buy a new or second hand item (clothing, electronic device)?</p> <p>Are there shared activities within your household to help reduce food waste, minimizing packaging... such as preparing leftovers together, recycling together, preparing weekly meal plan, fridge checking, sorting clothes,...</p> <p>Do the household members support each other in the circular economy practices?</p>
<p>The role of storytelling (can only be answered by the participants that have written a story after going through one or more challenges)</p>	<p><i>Motivation to share a story</i></p> <p>Do you like the idea of storytelling? Why or why not?</p> <p>What motivated you to share your personal story about circular practices?</p> <p>How did you felt while creating or writing your story?</p> <p>Did anything make it easier or harder for you to share your story?</p> <p><i>Perceived impact of stories</i></p> <p>Have you read or listened to other participants' stories? If yes, how did that affect you?</p> <p>Were there any particular stories that stayed with you? Why?</p>

	<p>Did these stories change the way you think about circular practices or influence your own behaviour?</p> <p>Do you feel writing the circular stories can improve or support your circular economy practices?</p> <p><i>Feelings of belonging and Identity development</i></p> <p>Did participating in the storytelling activity, including feedback and comments, affect your sense of connection with others in the project?</p> <p>Do you feel that telling or hearing stories helped you feel part of a community? Why, why not?</p> <p>Do you feel that telling or hearing stories influenced how you see yourself in relation to the idea of being a <i>Circular Citizen</i>?</p> <p><i>Suggestions for improvement</i></p> <p>What did you like most about the storytelling activity?</p> <p>Were there any aspects you found confusing, difficult, or unhelpful?</p> <p>What suggestions do you have to improve the experience of sharing and reading stories in the future?</p>
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7 Individual interviews

7.1 Overall purpose

The main objective of the individual interviews is to capture people’s attitudes and behaviours towards the circular economy practices in more detail than we can do with the quantitative questionnaires. The individual interviews will mainly focus on capturing people’s drivers and barriers of the circular economy practices which are part of the challenges across the different domains of CircleUp (e.g., food waste, packaging, textiles, electronic devices). Furthermore, we want to capture the households’ narratives and rationalities behind different circular economy practices

7.2 Interview guide and procedures

The questions that are part of the interview guideline can be found in Table 5. Although we will use semi-structured interviews, it is important to have some flexibility for the questions. The interview guideline should be tailored to the specific context of the country. The individual interview will be conducted at a single time point while we are actively working with the households during the project. The individual interviews should not last for more than one hour and should be conducted with 15-20 household members 14 years and older. All the interviews will be audio-recorded to ensure accuracy for the analysis afterwards. Furthermore, all data from the different individual interviews will be automatically transcribed and translated to English language to ensure accuracy of the interview analysis.

Based on the interview data, we will identify codes and categories relevant to the concept described above and advance our understating of alternative modes of consumption which are important in a circular economy society.

Since the CircleUp project covers various domains (food waste, packaging, electronics, and textiles) and the interviews should only last between 30 and 60 minutes, we will focus on one specific domain during each individual interview, guided by the interviewee’s lead and interest. The general questions at the beginning of the interview will be included in every interview.

In addition to the domain-based interviews, a supplementary set of interviews on the storytelling component will be conducted with a sample of 5–10 participants. These interviews aim to explore participants' experiences with the storytelling and the development of a circular citizen social identity. The interview guideline will draw on the questions used during the group discussions on this topic.

Table 5. Interview guidelines for the individual interviews

General questions regarding the circular economy and circular economy practices	<p>When you hear the world circular economy, what comes to your mind?</p> <p>What is circular economy for you?</p> <p>How important do you think it is to engage in circular economy practices such as reducing, reusing, repairing, or recycling?</p> <p>Which circular economy facilities are you familiar with?</p> <p>Which circular economy practices are you currently applying?</p> <p>What motivates you to participate in circular economy practices?</p>
Question related to material values	<p>What role do material things play in your life?</p> <p>How important is it to you to own new things (e.g., clothes, electronics)?</p> <p>Do you think living sustainably involves giving things up?</p> <p>How important is it to you to own things?</p> <p>Is it easy to you to share things you own? If so, why? Or why not?</p> <p>Do you feel that consumption gives you a sense of satisfaction or happiness?</p>
The role of storytelling	See table 4: Interview guidelines for the group discussion
FOOD	
Follow-up question(s)	<p>What do you usually do with the leftovers that are still edible?</p> <p>If you keep your leftovers, what do you usually do with prepared leftovers?</p> <p>What would help you in using leftovers?</p>
Knowledge question	What options are you aware of for reducing food waste?
Drivers and barriers for look, smell, taste method. Checking date labels	
Follow-up question	<p>What do you usually do with your food when the best before/use by dates expires?</p> <p>What would help you in checking the date labels?</p>
Impulsive shopping	
Follow-up question	<p>Do you buy food impulsively in the supermarket?</p> <p>If yes, what are the reasons for this?</p>
Storage of food	
Follow-up question	<p>What do you do to extend the durability of your food?</p> <p>What would help you in storing food?</p>
CLOTHES	
Buying new clothes	
Follow-up question	<p>When you buy a new clothing item, what are the reasons?</p> <p>Why do you buy secondhand clothes?</p>

	<p>What do you usually do with the clothes you don't need anymore?</p> <p>Period of use of clothes</p> <p>What would help you in reducing buying clothes?</p>
Sharing, swapping, renting and repairing clothes	
Follow-up question	<p>Why would you like/not like to share or rent your clothes with others?</p> <p>Why would you like to rent/not rent clothes?</p> <p>Reasons to (not) repair clothes?</p> <p>What would help you in sharing, renting and repairing more clothes?</p>
Knowledge question	What approaches are you familiar with for minimizing the purchase of new clothes?
ELECTRONICS	
Buying new electronic devices/buying second hand electronic devices	
Follow-up question	<p>When you a buy a new electronic device, what are the reasons?</p> <p>Why do you (not) buy second hand electronic devices?</p> <p>Period of use of electronics</p> <p>What would help you in buying less electronic devices?</p> <p>Reasons for no longer using an electronic device?</p>
Sharing, renting, and repairing electronic devices	
Follow-up question	<p>Why would you like/not like to share or rent electronic devices with others?</p> <p>Reasons to (not) repair electronic devices?</p> <p>What would help you in sharing, renting, and repairing more electronic devices?</p>
Recycling of electronic devices	
Follow-up question	<p>What do you usually do with the electronic devices you don't need anymore? Or the ones that are broken?</p> <p>Reasons for storing/discarding</p> <p>Why do you keep electronic devices that you don't use anymore/are broken?</p> <p>What would help you in recycling your electronic devices?</p>
Knowledge question	What do you know about strategies to avoid or reduce the purchase of new electronic devices?
PACKAGING	
Buying items in single-use packaging	
Follow-up question	<p>Do you think about the packaging when you buy a product? If no, why not?</p> <p>What would help you when considering reducing single-use packaging?</p>
Barriers and drivers for reusable packaging	
Follow-up question	<p>Why do you use/not use reusable coffee cup or lunch box?</p> <p>Why would you take a reusable container with you while shopping. Why not?</p>

	What would help you in using reusable lunch boxes, coffee cups?
Knowledge question	In what ways do you think single-use packaging can be reduced?
Circular stories	
The role of storytelling	See table 4: Interview guidelines for the group discussion

8 Behaviour observation

The qualitative and quantitative methods described so far will give insight into participant’s experience of particular circular behaviour and lifestyle changes. In addition, quantitative waste data will be automatically measured using smart bins. There will be separate bins for residual waste, plastic waste and one food waste. Whilst this multi-method approach will provide empirical richness it may still be unable to capture the full variety of household experiences, especially given the wide range of contexts in which households will be engaged. Therefore, the CircleUp project will also adopt ethnographic methods and specifically participant observation as a way to gather rich, contextual data which helps to give in-depth insights into each household’s experience, behaviours and environments. The aim will be to capture the nuances or individual factors which surveys or interviews might miss. For example, if a household experiences a disruptive life event (bereavement, job loss, health issue), participant observation may be able to capture these holistic factors to give context to the other data collected.

Given the primary aim of the participant observation is to be responsive and adaptive to the household context, the data collection protocol will be largely unstructured. Participant observation will be carried out by material efficiency advisors during and after each of their interactions with the households. The advisors will visit the participating households during the project to support them in overcoming barriers they face during the different CircleUp challenges. Visits can be organized physically or online, depending on the household’s preference.

All advisors will receive prior training in their respective countries, developed and provided by the CircleUp team. It is important that the material efficiency advisors are familiar with the local context and know the available circular economy practices in the area such as repair cafes, recycling centres, libraries, second hand shops etc.

The purpose of the visit is to provide support. The advisors could use guiding questions and checklists to structure their visits and provide some information to the households from waste sorting tips to suggesting local second hand shops. A set of guiding questions can be found in Table 6 to facilitate these conversations.

Advisors will give the households support and guidance by providing tailored advice and help based on each household’s needs, including practical tips and recommendations such as where to repair electronics, where to donate clothes or borrow some tools. In Table 7, a possible visit checklist is outlined for the material advisors.

During the visit, it is important that households feel comfortable and respected. Therefore whilst these protocols have been developed and will continue to be iterated, the main objective for the material efficiency advisors will be to build and maintain rapport and trust. The advisors will therefore be encouraged to prioritise flexibility and responsiveness in their interactions above adherence to a particular protocol.

Table 6. Questions for the behaviour observation

<p>ELECTRONIC DEVICES</p>	<p>What is going well with challenge XXX? Encourage participants to share positive experiences and tips that are already working and might help other households. Encourage participants to share this on the CircleUp platform.</p> <p>Are you facing any difficulties with challenge XXX? What is unclear? What exactly is hard to implement?</p> <p>Do you know any local services in your neighbourhood for recycling, repairing or sharing your devices?</p>
<p>FOOD</p>	<p>What is going well with challenge XXX? Encourage participants to share positive experiences and tips that are already working and might help other households. Encourage participants to share this on the CircleUp platform.</p> <p>Are you facing any difficulties with challenge XXX? What is unclear? What exactly is hard to implement?</p> <p>What is going well with challenge XXX?</p> <p>What can the household improve? Suggest some improvements with labelling of products, organisation in fridge, freezer or cupboards, reducing food waste, using leftovers, make meal plans, use shopping lists</p>
<p>CLOTHES</p>	<p>What is going well with challenge XXX? Encourage participants to share positive experiences and tips that are already working and might help other households. Encourage participants to share this on the CircleUp platform.</p> <p>Are you facing any difficulties with challenge XXX? What is unclear? What exactly is hard to implement?</p> <p>Are you interested in learning more about repairing or swapping clothes?</p>
<p>PACKAGING</p>	<p>What is going well with challenge XXX? Encourage participants to share positive experiences and tips that are already working and might help other households. Encourage participants to share this on the CircleUp platform.</p> <p>Are you facing any difficulties with challenge XXX? What is unclear? What exactly is hard to implement?</p> <p>Are you aware of any local options (markets) or refill shops in the neighbourhood?</p>

Table 7. Household visit checklist¹

Before the visit
Have a look at the households' background information (such as responses from the recruitment questionnaire or other any other available information provided by the households to CircleUp) during the recruitment process) to prepare yourself for your visit.
Make sure to tailor every individual visit to the household's needs.
Prepare your material for the visit such as: Household visit checklist The link for the survey Your computer to search for specific advice, tips... during the visit if needed Something to make notes on ...
Make sure to familiarize yourself with the circular economy services in the neighbourhood you will visit such as: Repair cafes Second hand shops Library Library tools Recycling centres Online sharing platforms Community fridges Refill shops
During the visit
Explain the purpose of the project (briefly)
Explain the purpose of the visit
Tell the household you will make notes during your visit
Have an informal chat with the household and ask about any difficulties or barriers they have encountered in adopting the circular practices from the CircleUp challenges. Use the observation questions (see Table 6) as a guideline.
Do not forget to ask what is going well.
Document key observations and household's feedback during the visit.
Towards the end of the visit
Summarize the main take aways from the visit for the household and discuss the next steps.
Tell the households where they can get more information, advice, and help with the CircleUp challenges if needed.
Do not forget to plan a follow-up visit if needed.

¹ This checklist was created with the support from AI.

9 Conclusion

Within this document, we have outlined the methodological framework of the CircleUp project, including its overall objectives, recruitment strategies, household selection criteria, and data methods. This framework is developed to investigate how the CircleUp households are engaging with circular economy practices and to evaluate the psychological and behavioural effects of the CircleUp intervention at the household level.

Within the CircleUp project, we will use both quantitative and qualitative research methods to ensure a comprehensive evaluation of behavioural change and the CircleUp project itself.

The quantitative methods include four similar survey questionnaires to see change in time. Furthermore, we will have LCA features developed in the CircleUp digital platform, to estimate the reduction of waste across four material streams: food, packaging, textiles, and electronics.

The qualitative methods consist of both group and individual interviews, which will give us deeper insights into participant's experiences, attitudes, and perceptions. These perspectives are necessary to understand the motivations behind potential circularity behavioural changes and the effectiveness of the intervention.

For the following months, the CircleUp team will focus on the following activities:

During the upcoming project meeting in September 2025, the team will work together to reduce the length of the surveys and the interviews to motivate households to stay engaged.

We will conduct a pilot test of the survey questionnaires to ensure clarity, relevance, and reliability before the full implementation. All the materials will be translated to the language of the participating households (English, German, Latvian, and Norwegian).

The tailored recruitment strategies will be further developed to reach the target of 100 participating households.

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